

Bird migration model 2.0: implemented changes and comparison with Model 1.1

Maja Bradarić, Bart Kranstauber and Judy Shamoun-Baranes

University of Amsterdam, Institute for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Dynamics, PO Box 94240, 1090 GE Amsterdam

Project manager: prof. dr. Judy Shamoun-Baranes

Date of publication: June 2025

The report should be cited as:

Bradarić M, Kranstauber B & Shamoun-Baranes J. 2025. Bird migration model 2.0: implemented changes and comparison with model 1.1. University of Amsterdam.

This work was supported by the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management - Rijkswaterstaat (project number 31184728) through "Start-stop project" and "Wind at sea" (WOZEP) programmes.

Contents

Summary	3
Background	4
Implemented changes	5
ERA5 data	5
Predictor variables	6
Phenology	7
Accumulation at departure	9
Comparison Model 1.1. and Model 2.0	11
Main model evaluation	12
Conclusions	14
1. Elements explored but ultimately not included in the model	16
Using data from highly correlated radar locations to fill in the gaps in the data	16
Extension of the prediction period.....	16
Smaller number of predictor variables	16
Include weather conditions at departure in Norway as predictors	16
Weights.....	16
2. Data vs predictions time series	17
Spring	17
Autumn.....	19
3. ROC curves	21
Spring	21
Autumn.....	22
4. Cumulative migration plots.....	23
Spring	23
Autumn.....	24

Summary

In this report, we provide an overview of the changes implemented in the latest bird migration prediction model, Model 2.0, which are the result of additional research conducted at UvA (University of Amsterdam) and input from the teams manually predicting migration for the start/stop procedure, conducting radar data analysis (Waardenburg Ecology) and operationalizing the model predictions (Technolution).

Changes implemented in the Model 2.0 development occurred on multiple levels and include data-level changes, selection of predictor variables, and structural model changes. The main changes include:

1. Longer time series (Model 2.0 trained with spring and autumn data from Luchterduinen radar location between 2019 and 2024)
2. Data augmentation (SMOTE) was performed for balancing the data
3. Adapted bird accumulation variables to introduce estimated bird departure variables
4. Adapted phenology variables
5. Excluded variables that represented nightly differences in bird accumulations due to wind assistance and precipitation
6. Adjusted model hyperparameters

Model 2.0 performs considerably better than Model 1.1 in terms of general accuracy, variance explained, as well as precision and recall. The level of improvement varies from year to year, but is visible in all test years. The general increase in precision and recall resulted in fewer false negatives and a higher number of true positives. A higher number of false positives is observed as a direct consequence of applying the SMOTE technique. We demonstrate that across testing years, the percentage of migrants saved within 30 hours of the highest intensity migration with Model 2.0 is several times higher in both seasons than when predicting with Model 1.1. Nevertheless, there is still room for future improvement, which will likely occur with the collection of more data and the development of improved technologies for tracking birds at sea using radars to decrease the periods during which the data is affected by various forms of clutter. Alternatively, modelling approaches that take a migration system-wide approach might be beneficial, but are currently operationally challenging.

Background

As part of the start-stop project, coordinated by Rijkswaterstaat, the bird migration prediction model is being used to inform curtailments of offshore wind turbines in the Dutch North Sea during intense bird migration events. The first version of this model (Model 1.0) was delivered in 2022 and replaced with the second version (Model 1.1) in 2023, after additional radar data were collected for model training. The model's performance is evaluated on a half-yearly basis by an independent team of ecologists (Waardenburg Ecology), and its operation is closely monitored by data scientists (Technolution), as well as the team of ornithologists responsible for independent migration predictions. All these parties evaluate model performance under different migration events and give recommendations for potential model improvements.

Concurrently, more radar data have been collected offshore for model training and evaluation. Data availability, especially the availability of moments of intense migration (which generally occur on a few nights during a migration season), has been identified as one of the primary challenges in achieving accurate predictions of intense bird migration (Bradarić et al, 2024; Middelveld et al, 2023; Kuijper et al, 2025). Therefore, longer data timeseries are generally expected to improve model performance.

Since the development of Model 1.0, a team of UvA scientists conducting interdisciplinary research that combines ecology, meteorology, and data science has further explored migration patterns across the North Sea. This was made possible by the deployment of additional offshore radars at various locations in the North Sea. Besides providing the first overview of broader spatiotemporal bird migration patterns across the North Sea, the insights collected during this research have contributed to identifying the adaptations needed for further model development (Bradarić & Shamoun-Baranes, 2025). One of the aspects explored during this research was whether a separate model for the Zeeland region is necessary. High correlations across radars in Luchterduinen and the Zeeland region indicated that the patterns are quite comparable (Bradarić & Shamoun-Baranes, 2025). Patterns at the Gemini location showed that a separate model might be beneficial for the region around the Gemini wind park, as the radar at this location generally has low correlation with radars in the southern North Sea (Bradarić & Shamoun-Baranes, 2025). However, the model development for the Gemini region was out of the scope of the current project.

Therefore, using novel research findings, input from various expert teams, and additional data, the team at UvA has developed a new bird migration prediction model (Model 2.0) based on data collected at the Luchterduinen location, which provides a good representation of migration patterns across the southern North Sea. The changes and updates applied to Model 2.0 are presented in this report. The primary goal of developing the new model version was to increase model accuracy, particularly when predicting intense migration.

Implemented changes

Changes implemented in Model 2.0 occurred on multiple levels and include data-level changes, changes in predictor variables, and structural model changes. Below, we provide a more detailed explanation of these changes.

Data

Timeseries length

For Model 2.0 training, an extra year of data (spring and autumn 2024) was used. Longer data time series improve model accuracy primarily through contributing more moments of intense bird migration from which the model can learn. Model 2.0 has been trained using radar data from the Luchterduinen radar location (52.25 N, 4.10 E), collected during the period of peak migration in spring (15 February – 30 April) and autumn (1 October – 30 November) of 2019 – 2024, a year longer than Model 1.1. The shortened migration season aims to reduce noise in the data and focus on the period of intense migration; all peaks occurred during the periods included in the model training (Bradarić et al., 2024; Bradarić & Shamoun-Baranes, 2025).

Imbalanced data and Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE)

Due to the nature of bird migration, which typically has periods of low migration and a few pulses of intense migration, the training data used is highly imbalanced, containing many more hours of low-intensity migration than those with high-intensity migration. Shortening the migration period used for model training was one way to decrease the imbalance in the data (Bradarić et al, 2024).

However, even after doing that, the training data still has only a few moments of peak migration. As the aim is to correctly predict peak moments while limiting false positive predictions, methods for data balancing needed to be applied. In Models 1.0 and 1.1, this was addressed through stratified sampling (see Bradarić et al., 2024). In Model 2.0, as suggested by Technolution (Kuijper et al, 2025), the synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTE) adjusted for regression was employed.

Generally, SMOTE is a type of data augmentation where the minority subset of the data is oversampled. Here, we used the *SmoteRegress* function from the UBL R package (Branco et al, 2016). The algorithm generated synthetic data points for underrepresented cases (high-intensity migration) by interpolating between existing instances, using a Manhattan distance metric to identify nearest neighbours. The threshold for defining a rare (minority) case was set to 0.95, meaning that any observation above the seasonal 95th percentile of MTR data was considered rare and oversampled. We used an oversampling rate of 20, which means that for every data point of the rare observations (high-intensity migration), 20 synthetic ones were created. In contrast, the majority group (low-intensity migration) stayed unchanged. This was implemented before model training for the spring and autumn migration seasons separately..

ERA5 data

ERA5 reanalysis data were re-downloaded, and weather variables for all years recalculated using the same methodology as described in Bradarić et al 2024. This was necessary due to potential changes in variable calculations due to updates of models that are generating ERA5 data. The data processing code was also updated to accommodate changes in data storage applied by ECMWF.

Predictor variables

After testing different combinations and numbers of predictor variables, the best model performance was obtained with the subset of variables used in Model 1.1. All variables that represented nightly differences in accumulation due to wind assistance and precipitation were replaced with estimated departures due to wind assistance and precipitation at the respective departure locations. These estimated departure variables represent proportions of birds that accumulated in the previous night and the theoretical numbers of birds arriving on the respective night (based on seasonal phenology in Figure 1). The theoretical accumulation and migration depend on the wind assistance and precipitation. For more details, see the accumulation section. See Table 1 for a complete list of predictor variables included in the model training process.

Table 1. Overview of variables used for model training in spring and autumn. Variables with the asterisk (*) next to them represent those that were amongst the top 10 variables by variable importance (those most contributing to the model) in all combinations of training years.

Spring	Autumn
Hourly phenology*	Hourly phenology*
Yearly phenology*	Yearly phenology
WA towards NE radar location*	WA towards SW at radar location*
WA towards E radar location*	WA towards W at radar location*
Total precipitation at the radar location	Total precipitation at the radar location
Wind assistance in the UK	Mean sea level pressure at the radar location*
Total precipitation in the UK	Total precipitation in N Netherlands
Nightly difference in mean sea level pressure in the UK	Estimated departure due to precipitation in N Netherlands*
Estimated departure due to WA in the UK*	Temperature at N Netherlands
Estimated departure due to precipitation in the UK	Estimated departure due to WA in N Netherlands*
Estimated departure due to WA and precipitation in the UK*	Estimated departure due to WA and precipitation in N Netherlands*
Accumulation due to precipitation in the UK	Accumulation due to WA in N Netherlands
Wind assistance in France	Accumulation due to precipitation in N Netherlands
Total precipitation in France	Total precipitation in NW Germany
Mean sea level pressure in France*	Mean sea level pressure in NW Germany
Temperature in France	Nightly difference in mean sea level pressure in NW Germany
Estimated departure due to WA in France	Estimated departure due to WA in NW Germany
Estimated departure due to precipitation in France	Estimated departure due to precipitation in NW Germany
Estimated departure due to WA and precipitation in France	Estimated departure due to WA and precipitation in NW Germany
	Accumulation due to WA in NW Germany
	Accumulation due to precipitation in NW Germany
	Wind assistance in Denmark
	Temperature in Denmark
	Estimated departure due to WA in Denmark
	Estimated departure due to precipitation in Denmark
	Estimated departure due to WA and precipitation in Denmark
	Accumulation due to WA in Denmark*
	Accumulation due to precipitation in Denmark

Phenology

Seasonal and nightly phenology variables were updated to reflect a 6-year seasonal bird migration pattern. Generalised additive models were fit to data using day of year and hour after sunset as a predictor variable, and MTR as a response variable, as described in Bradarić & Shamoun-Baranes, 2025. Updated seasonal (Figure 3) and hourly (Figure 4) phenology curves are presented below. These curves are also used to estimate the numbers of birds arriving at departure locations in accumulation functions as described above.

Figure 1. Seasonal phenology curves in spring (upper panel) and autumn (lower panel). The black line represents the modelled relationship between MTR (birds/km/hr) and day of year. The grey band denotes 95% confidence intervals, which indicate variation among nights.

Figure 2. Hourly phenology curves in spring (upper panel) and autumn (lower panel). The black line represents the modelled relationship between MTR (birds/km/hr) and hours after sunset. The grey band denotes 95% confidence intervals, which indicate variation among nights.

Accumulation at departure

When weather conditions are not favourable for migration for a few days, birds that would otherwise depart may accumulate in large numbers and depart simultaneously once weather conditions improve. This has been observed along coastlines for birds that need to embark on a journey across the sea (Buler & Moore, 2011). To simulate accumulation behaviour, Models 1.0 and 1.1 simulate a fraction of accumulated birds due to wind assistance and precipitation at various departure locations. A binary threshold was used to estimate when $2/3$ of the birds that would otherwise depart will accumulate following Erni et al, 2002.

In Model 2.0, we updated accumulation functions to estimate the number of birds accumulating and departing each night, depending on weather conditions and seasonal phenology (Figure 1), which serves as a long-term average and a proxy for the number of birds passing through. This adaptation incorporates one of the suggestions from the bird migration prediction team to include an estimate of birds flying over the radar location (note this is not based on the actual observations of birds flying by), thereby avoiding predictions of intense migration when most birds have already departed.

a)

b)

Figure 3. **a)** Gaussian (bell-shaped) curve describing departures due to wind assistance in spring and **b)** sigmoid function describing departures due to wind assistance in autumn.

When calculating accumulation due to wind assistance at departure locations in spring, we described the fraction of birds departing using a Gaussian (bell-shaped) function that depends on wind assistance (WA) (Figure 3, upper panel). This means birds were most likely to leave when wind conditions were close to an optimal wind assistance of 6 m/s (μ), and departures became less likely when wind conditions were worse or better than this value, with the drop-off determined by σ (which controls how sensitive departures are to changes in wind). In autumn, departures depend on wind assistance, modelled as a sigmoid function (Figure 3, lower panel). The seasonal difference in functions describing departures is due to different responses to wind observed in different seasons (Bradarić et al, 2020). In spring, birds seem to have an optimal wind assistance, while in autumn, due to the unavailability of tailwinds, they tend to be more flexible in their choice of wind conditions at departure (Bradarić et al, 2020). Therefore, the number of birds migrating will increase with increased wind assistance, with minimal wind assistance required for departure.

For accumulation due to precipitation at different departure locations, an exponential decay function was used to express that birds will be less likely to leave as precipitation increases (Figure 4), with departures dropping sharply when precipitation was above 1 mm. The steepness of this drop is controlled by a parameter called λ .

Figure 4. Exponential decay function describing departures due to precipitation. tp indicates the variable name in the ERA5 dataset.

In addition to separate accumulations due to wind assistance and precipitation, a joint accumulation predictor due to both wind assistance and precipitation at different departure locations was calculated. This accumulation resulted from the interaction between wind assistance and precipitation, following the same seasonal functions described above and phenology. This was implemented to limit the number of estimated departures when wind assistance conditions are good, but birds still might not depart due to rain.

Comparison Model 1.1. and Model 2.0

In this section, we present different evaluation metrics for Model 1.1 and Model 2.0. Table 2 provides an overview of evaluation metrics and their corresponding representations. Note that metrics such as area under the curve (AUC), precision, recall, f1, as well as confusion matrices and cumulative migration plots, can only be produced for the hours during which observation data is available. In spring, the hours were 671 in 2019, 564 in 2020, 769 in 2021, 706 in 2022, and 741 in 2023. In autumn, the hours were 610 in 2019, 467 in 2020, 551 in 2021, 617 in 2022, and 392 in 2023. The models presented here were always trained in a way that one year was excluded from the training process and used as a test and evaluation year. Note that this approach has been used only for evaluation purposes, and the final model delivered to RWS was trained with all available years of data (spring and autumn 2019-2024). Yearly evaluation plots and timeseries are available in the appendix. All threshold-dependent evaluations used thresholds of 150 birds/km/h for spring and 173 birds/km/h for autumn. These thresholds are currently used in the operational part of the wind turbine curtailments.

Table 2. Overview of the main model evaluation metrics and their meanings. The actual average values across years for Model 1.1 and Model 2.2 are presented in Figures 5 and 7. TP=true positives, FP=false positives and FN=false negatives. All metrics with an asterisk (*) were calculated based on thresholds of 150 birds/km/h for spring and 173 birds/km/h for autumn.

Metric	Meaning	Range	How to read
OOB R²	Variance in target explained by model (out-of-bag in Random Forest)	can be < 0, 0 to 1	1 = perfect fit; 0 = no better than mean; < 0 = worse than predicting mean. Higher = better fit.
AUC	Probability model ranks a random positive above a random negative (ROC AUC)	0 to 1	1 = perfect discrimination; 0.5 = random guessing; closer to 1 = better discrimination.
RMSE	Average magnitude of prediction errors (root of mean squared error)	≥ 0 (depends on units of target)	Lower = better. 0 = perfect predictions.
Accuracy*	Proportion of total correct predictions (TP + TN / All cases)	0 to 1	Higher = better. 1 = all correct; 0 = none correct.
Precision*	Proportion of predicted positives that are actually positive (TP / (TP + FP))	0 to 1	Higher = better. 1 = no false positives. Significant when false positives are costly.
Recall*	Proportion of actual positives correctly predicted (TP / (TP + FN))	0 to 1	Higher = better. 1 = no false negatives.
F1*	Harmonic mean of precision and recall	0 to 1	Higher = better. 1 = perfect balance of precision and recall.

Main model evaluation

Overall, Model 2.0 exhibits better performance than Model 1.1 across years in different seasons (Figure 5), although the level of improvement varies by year (Appendix 2, 3, and 4). In both seasons, the number of false negatives decreased considerably for most years, while the number of false positives increased (Figure 6), a direct consequence of applying the SMOTE technique for data augmentation. Even though precision and recall generally improved in Model 2.0, they are still low from a data science perspective (ideally, they should be above 0.7; however, when dealing with dynamic processes such as bird migration, 0.5 or 0.6 would also be acceptable). Higher precision means that Model 2.0 is better at predicting true positives.

Spring

Autumn

Figure 5. The main model metrics across years (n=5) in spring and autumn. The meanings of the different metrics are provided in Table 2. Red boxplots represent the new model's metrics (Model 2.0), while green boxplots represent the old model's metrics (Model 1.1). The boxplots represent the interquartile range (IQR) of the metric values (25th to 75th percentile), and the horizontal bold line represents the median value of the metric across years. The whiskers represent the spread starting from Q3 to the highest data point (upper whisker) and Q1 to the lowest data point (lower whisker), while dots represent outliers. Note that not all the hours for which predictions were available had matching radar observations. For the exact number of available evaluation hours per year, please see the beginning of this section.

Spring

Autumn

Figure 6. Confusion matrices in spring (upper panel) and autumn (lower panel) per year showing the number of hours that were classified as true positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN) and false negatives (FN) above or below the threshold of 150 (spring) and 173 (autumn). Darker shades represent a higher number of observations within each class. Note that not all the hours for which predictions were available had matching radar observations. For the exact number of available evaluation hours per year, please see the beginning of this section.

ROC curves, which show the trade-off between true positive and false positive rate across thresholds (Appendix 3), and cumulative percentage plots, which illustrate how migration percentage accumulates over ranked predictions hours (Figure 7, Appendix 4), show that Model 2.0 is generally closer to observations than Model 1.1. With Model 2.0, it is possible to save a much higher percentage of seasonal migration within 30 hours than with Model 1.1. For example, in 2021, the percentage of migrants saved within 30 hours with Model 2.0 is four times higher in spring and almost two times higher in autumn than when predicting with Model 1.1.

Figure 7. Cumulative percentage of total nocturnal migration per hour in spring (left) and autumn (right) of 2021, for which the radar data were available. The percentage of seasonal migration in each available migration hour was calculated and then summed to get a cumulative percentage. The black line represents the cumulative percentages when the measured migration hours were ranked based on the measured MTR in descending order (hours with the highest measured MTR in the left corner of the figure). The green and red lines represent the cumulative percentages of measured MTR when the migration hours are ranked in descending order based on the MTRs predicted by the old model, Model 1.1 (green) and the new model, Model 2.0 (red). Note that the values represented by green and red lines are the measured hourly percentages of the total seasonal migration. Numbers in plots represent the percentages of birds saved by each of the models at a 30-hour cutoff. Plots for other years are available in Appendix 4.

Conclusions

Overall, based on a range of assessment criteria, Model 2.0 is an improvement over Model 1.1 for wind turbine curtailment purposes, where the focus is on predicting instances of peak migration. Here we describe several extra considerations that may be valuable for assessment and curtailment in the future. Precision and recall are very sensitive to the thresholds selected for assessment and were calculated using the current operational curtailment thresholds. In practice, the thresholds could be adjusted to account for newly collected data, which may reflect improved recall and precision.

In addition, it needs to be noted that we do a binary classification (intense migration or not) of a continuous variable (birds/km/hr). Small prediction errors around the threshold could result in a FP or FN, but the continuous prediction might not be that far off. We therefore recommend that curtailment results should not only be evaluated on the basis of the binary classification but also on a

continuous scale. In other words, migration intensity might not have crossed the threshold on a night when it would have been predicted, but it still might be a night when a considerable number of birds have been protected, thus meeting the objective of start/stop procedures. Another challenge with model assessment is that data is missing for many hours, hindering the possibility of assessing the model's performance. Overall, there is still room for improvement. Smaller improvements could be achieved by extending the data time series, while larger improvements will emerge from reducing noise in the data through further refinement of the data filtering as new adaptations and technologies emerge. Other approaches that could result in a more transformative change in model performance would be investigating the integration of other datasets, such as observations in departure regions, or modelling approaches that take a migration system-wide approach, which are currently operationally challenging.

Acknowledgements

We thank the bird migration expert team, our colleagues from Technolution, Rijkswaterstaat, and Waardenburg Ecology, for their valuable input, which contributed to the development of Model 2.0. Special thanks to Johannes de Groeve (UvA) for optimising the data extraction queries. This work makes use of the Dutch National e-infrastructure with the support of the SURF cooperative.

References

- Bradarić M, Bouten W, Fijn RC, Krijgsveld KL and Shamoun-Baranes J. 2020. Winds at departure shape seasonal patterns of nocturnal bird migration over the North Sea. *Journal of Avian Biology* 51(10).
- Buler J. J. & Moore, F. R. 2011. Migrant-habitat relationships during stopover along an ecological barrier: Extrinsic constraints and conservation implications. *Journal of Ornithology* 152: 101-112.
- Bradarić M, Kranstauber B, Bouten W & Shamoun-Baranes J. 2024. Forecasting nocturnal bird migration for dynamic aeroconservation: the value of short-term datasets. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 61(6): 1147-1158.
- Bradarić M & Shamoun-Baranes J. 2025. Time for barrier crossing: nocturnal bird migration phenology of the North Sea. University of Amsterdam.
- Branco P, Ribeiro RP & Torgo L. 2016. UBL: an R Package for Utility-Based Learning, CoRR abs/1604.08079 [cs.MS], URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1604.0807>
- Erni B, Liechti F, Bruderer B & Underhill L. G. 2002. Wind and rain govern the intensity of nocturnal bird migration in central Europe—A log-linear regression analysis. *Ardea* 90(1): 155–166.
- Kuijper C, Dubbeldam M & Roggekamp W. 2025. Adviesrapport Machine Learning Model, versie 1.1. Technolution.
- Middelveld RP, Kraal JJ and Gyimesi A. 2024. Validation of the outcomes of the bird migration prediction model for 2023. Report 24-114. Waardenburg Ecology, Culemborg.

Appendix

1. Elements explored but ultimately not included in the model

Stricter data filtering

It has been suggested by Waardenburg Ecology to include stricter filtering thresholds, which would exclude more data. As this step would exclude even more hours from an already noisy dataset, we decided against it now.

Using data from highly correlated radar locations to fill in the gaps in the data

This has been tested between Borssele and Luchterduinen, as well as between HKZA and Luchterduinen radars. The test showed that they usually lacked data at the same moments, and it was decided no to implement this in the modelling procedure.

Extension of the prediction period

As the model is being run throughout the full bird migration period (February 15 to May 31 in spring; August 15 to November 30 in autumn), it was discussed to also train it with the data from the full migration period instead of focusing on the period when most of the intense migration occurs (February 15 to April 30 in spring; October 1 to November 30 in autumn). In discussion with RWS, it was decided to limit the model training data to the periods when we expect the most intense bird migration, in order to reduce the amount of noise in the data and keep the training data more balanced.

Smaller number of predictor variables

Technolution has suggested that decreasing the number of predictor variables might improve model performance, as the number of variables used in Model 1.1 might have been too high for the amount of data used for training (Kuijper et al, 2025). Therefore, the model was set up with varying combinations and numbers of variables, and the model performance was tested. Decreasing the number of variables generally decreased the model performance, and the variables included in Model 2.0 (Table 1) were the ones which resulted in the best overall model performance. Additionally, the number of observations in the training data used in Model 2.0 was increased by the SMOTE technique, considerably increasing the size of the dataset, and the number of variables is more in line with the dataset size.

Include weather conditions at departure in Norway as predictors

We downloaded and calculated all departure area predictor variables for the Norway location and tested the model performance after their inclusion in the predictor variables. Different combinations of models, which contained predictor variables from departure areas in Norway, showed inferior model performance to the setup we currently use for Model 2.0.

Weights

Adding weights to observations during the modelling procedure (e.g. favouring observations of intense-migration hours) can help increase model performance when dealing with imbalanced datasets. However, when the SMOTE technique is already applied, adding weights can be counterproductive and can lead to model overfitting. We tested adding weights to predictor variables, but this resulted in inferior model performance to the setup we currently use in Model 2.0.

2. Data vs predictions time series

Seasonal time series of hourly values predicted by Model 1.1 (old) and Model 2.0 (new) compared against observed values (black line) in different testing years.

Spring

Observed vs Predicted 2021

Observed vs Predicted 2022

Observed vs Predicted 2023

Autumn

Observed and Predicted MTR_harm – 2019

Observed and Predicted MTR_harm – 2020

Observed and Predicted MTR_harm – 2021

Observed and Predicted MTR_harm – 2022

Observed and Predicted MTR_harm – 2023

3. ROC curves

The receiver operating curves (ROC) for the spring and autumn models were created with a threshold of 150 birds/km/h in spring and 173 birds/km/h in autumn (current thresholds used in operation). Red lines represent the performance of the new model (Model 2.0), and the green lines represent the old model (Model 1.1). These plots demonstrate the model's effectiveness in identifying hours with high migration intensity while minimising the fraction of false positive predictions.

Spring

Autumn

4. Cumulative migration plots

The figures below show the cumulative percentage of total nocturnal migration during hours in spring and autumn, for which the radar data were available. The percentage of seasonal migration in each available migration hour was calculated and then summed to get a cumulative percentage. The black line represents the cumulative percentages when the measured migration hours were ranked based on the measured MTR in descending order (hours with the highest measured MTR in the left corner of the figure). The green and red lines represent the cumulative percentages of measured MTR when the migration hours are ranked in descending order based on the MTRs predicted by Model 1.1 (green) and Model 2.0 (red). Note that the values represented by green and red lines are the measured hourly percentages of the total seasonal migration. Numbers in plots represent the percentages of birds saved by each of the models at a 30-hour cutoff.

Spring

Autumn

Model — new — observed — old

Model — new — observed — old

Model — new — observed — old

Model — new — observed — old